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The Consequences of Covid-19 on Youth Mental Health

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ABSTRACT

During epidemics, the quantity of individuals whose emotional well-being is influenced will in general be more noteworthy than the quantity of individuals influenced by the disease. Previous disasters have demonstrated that the mental health consequences can last longer and have a higher incidence than the pandemic itself, and that the psychological and economic consequences can be incalculable when considered in diverse situations. The COVID-19 pandemic has ramifications in other areas as well, including family organisation, school, company, and public place closures, changes in work routines, and isolation, which can lead to emotions of helplessness and abandonment. Furthermore, the economic and societal ramifications of such a large-scale catastrophe may exacerbate insecurity. The COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown have brought about a sense of fear and anxiety around the globe. This phenomenon has led to short-term as well as long-term psychosocial and mental health implications, especially among the youths. Many vulnerability factors, such like developmental age, educational status, pre-existing mental health disorders, being impoverished, or being confined due to infection or fear of infection, determine the quality and extent of the impact upon youths. An attempt has been made in this paper to study the mental health aspects of the youths impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. This study will try to find out the various impact on the mental health of the youths, its root causes along with some suggestive measures to get rid of such mental illness. It will be qualitative research in nature. Data will be collected from 25 youth who are students through telephonic interviews using an interview schedule.

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KEYWORDS

Covid-19, mental-health, physical health, youths, psychosocial, mental- hygiene, trauma

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INTRODUCTION

Humans are infected with Covid 19, a virus that causes both mental and physical sickness. As a contagious virus, it can readily travel from an infected person into the air by coughing or sneezing the virus into the air to a healthy human being who breathes or unintentionally touches the virus. Precaution is seen to be the most effective approach to combat the epidemic. When the WHO proclaimed Novel Corona Virus a pandemic on March 11, 2020, the first step in combating the illness was to impose a severe lockdown to treat, identify, and reduce the virus's spread. With existing issues like as a massive population of 1.35 billion people spread across several states, poverty, socioeconomic inequality, and lockdown, developing countries like India have become a major challenge not only for the government but also for each individual.

As there are no formal criteria for defining youth, we might describe it as the era of transition from childhood to adulthood, when a person is capable of surviving on their own. For our purposes, youth is defined as a person who is capable of standing on their own, making their own decisions, and figuring out how to survive and leave society. Without the youth's ongoing contribution, no country can endure. The youth must be properly nourished since they represent the country. Fear of young has always been a hindrance to the country. As there are no formal criteria for defining youth, we might describe it as the era of transition from childhood to adulthood, when a person is capable of surviving on their own. For our purposes, youth is defined as a person who is capable of standing on their own, making their own decisions, and figuring

out how to survive and leave society. Without the youth's ongoing contribution, no country can endure. The youth must be properly nourished since they represent the country. Fear of young has always been a hindrance to the country.

This research will look at numerous effects on youth mental health as well as their reactions to those impacts. This research will aid in the investigation of numerous mental health concerns that have arisen as a result of the Covid 19 pandemic and lockdown. It will be a qualitative study in the wild. Data will be gathered utilising telephonic interviews and some open-ended questions.

Statement of the Problem

Mental health and well-being are the foundation and pillars for dealing with life's different stresses and obstacles. Our health has always been a top issue for us as humans, whether we are aware of it or not. Our priorities as teenagers may shift, but the consequences always have an impact on our mental health. Mood and outlook, social self, drive and motivation, core cognition, mind-body link, and other characteristics are all taken into account while evaluating mental health. These factors may differ from one person to the next.

Because India is a young country with nearly half of the population under the age of 25, thinking about their mental health is a major worry. Following the covid pandemic, a huge population of India's youth were vulnerable to the virus. In an attempt to reduce the number of people infected, all precautionary efforts have had both positive and negative effects on the youth. It cannot be argued that the lockdown was effective, but it came at a heavy cost, both financially and

psychologically, to the youngsters. According to studies, the absolute ban on selling alcohol during lockdown induced alcohol withdrawal syndrome in many young people, many of whom were previously unknown. Many students are afraid of missing out on tremendous possibilities for higher education, and with all of the trauma going on, sadness and anxiety are common, which society refuses to recognise, leading to many adolescents attempting suicide.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In their research, MEI (2020) discovered that mental health is a severe problem among youth amid public health emergencies. Low educational levels, PTSD symptoms, enterprise employee, and bad coping techniques are among the elements that influence juvenile mental health, according to the study. As a result, the local government is being urged to conduct adequate health-care initiatives. If someone experiences a traumatic event, according to Ehlers and Clark's (2002) report on posttraumatic stress disorder, they may make a negative assessment of the trauma. It makes it simpler to use maladaptive coping mechanisms to keep PTSD symptoms like invasion, arousal, and intense negative emotions at bay.

As a result, it is assumed in this study that after experiencing traumatic events, adolescent groups have a tendency to acquire psychological disorders. On February 18, 2020, the National Health Commission of China updated that the COVID-19 outbreak in China has produced panic among citizens and resulted in mental health

stress, which is of equal concern to the public as the pandemic itself. According to J Formos Med Assoc. (2010), the SARS 2003 pandemic and the 2009 Novel Influenza A (H1N1) outbreak caused the public to suffer from PTSD, sadness, and anxiety. PTSD has been linked to sadness and anxiety in certain studies. According to Clark and Ehlers' idea, traumatic occurrences may result in a negative mental and physical assessment of the trauma, making it easier to adapt to PTSD symptoms. As a result of the research, it was concluded that young people had a higher risk of developing psychiatric problems as a result of traumatic stress disorder.

METHODOLOGY

The qualitative approach is used in the research, which includes both primary and secondary data. Purposive sampling is used to select respondents for data collecting. For the objective of the study, 17 young people from Guwahati were chosen as respondents. As a source of secondary data, many publications and journals are examined.

Objectives:

- To investigate the difficulties faced by youths as a result of the pandemic.
- To learn more about the pandemic's effects on young people's mental health.
- To determine what steps may be taken to address these issues.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

According to the findings of the aforesaid study, the majority of those who replied were extremely vulnerable to the continuing sensitive covid 19 pandemic time. Mood and outlook, social self, drive and motivation, core cognition, mind-body link, and other characteristics are evaluated while evaluating an individual's mental health. These factors may differ from one person to the next. Depression and anxiety, which are most commonly found in teenagers these days, have increased dramatically, along with severe functional impairment and the risk that comes with it. Fear of loss of income, social interaction, and illness has caused tremendous stress on the youth.

Considering the age as a factor in the verse of adulthood, social acceptance and personal safety can disrupt the only integrity of the youth, the pillar on which almost every youth relies. As a result, many activities that provide structure, daily rhythm, and significance to the kids, such as school, collages, extracurricular activities, physical labour, and social connections, have vanished. It has also been discovered that during lockdowns caused by the closure of educational facilities, home isolations have created confusion in the educational system. In the end, this causes anxiety and negative views about the youth's job prospects.

Many participants reported that these losses had exacerbated their depressive symptoms tremendously during the first few months, causing social detachment and emptiness within

oneself, which were observed to be nearly equal for most people staying near or away from their homes. According to the poll, the majority of the symptoms were temporary, and the participants were seen to be aware of the issues they were facing and eager to take safeguards. During the lockdown, most of the youth returned home to face a long period of waiting for acceptance of the ongoing family environment, as youth health, both mentally and physically, is influenced by their family system, which is impacted during the pandemic, and is made even worse when someone close to the family is affected. Family may become a risk factor for adolescents, despite being expected to be a positive aspect.

During the epidemic, family assets such as money and food are extremely valuable. With other family members going through their own breakdowns and losses, the youth are expected to play a significant role in the family, which is a new experience for most of them. Domestic violence and conflict among siblings has also become a big concern for their own and others. According to the data Most of the youth has considered it to be a good experience as they are finding ways to be a better version of themselves for everybody. During unlock down maintaining social distance is also a big concern for the youth.

CONCLUSION

From the above objective it can be concluded that, the COVID-19 pandemic is a disaster that has affected the human beings at multiple level and its impact is yet to be thoroughly understood

in the future. With the considerable evidence it can be observed that this pandemic has affected the wellbeing of the youth at psychological level. As WHO has warned the powerful nations and the governments how to prepare and to tackle the mental health complication that is most likely to arise due to COVID-19. As the evident indicate that there are many complications related to mental health in youth our knowledge of the impact cause during the pandemic on youth mental health is restricted to limited data and observations. Mostly the lack of awareness and the fear of social separation and neglecting the direct impact of COvid-19 is the root cause preventing the youth to present their views. Hence most of the research mostly focuses on understanding and exploring the mental health problem of elderly people rather than the youth generation. But with the concrete evidence it can't be neglected that Psychological distress associated with depression and anxiety is highly frequent and widely spreading in adolescents and youth which is now fueled by Covid-19. So it is

high time that many steps that need to be taken by both Government, parents and the youth itself to maintain a good mental health and psychological wellbeing of the youth who are in the most crucial phase of their lives.

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